

SIMULATE5-K Verification and Qualification for BWR Stability Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This study contributes to the qualification of the transient code SIMULATE5-K (S5K) for boiling water reactor (BWR) stability analysis and the optimization of its input models, supporting Axpo's transition from SIMULATE-3K (S3K) for transient simulations at the Leibstadt Nuclear Power Plant (KKL). To this aim, a systematic sensitivity analysis was performed using a core-only model of 40 historical stability tests conducted at KKL to assess physical accuracy, numerical performance, and the influence of modeling assumptions on stability predictions.

The results show that S5K successfully reproduces the expected physical trends for most parameters, demonstrating reliable physics verification within the study's scope. The only notable exception is the fuel-to-cladding gap conductance, which exhibited inconsistent behavior and will require further investigation. Numerical optimization studies identified optimal configurations for axial nodalization and neutronics/thermal-hydraulic time-step size, achieving an effective balance between numerical diffusion reduction and computational efficiency.

Overall, the findings of this study constitute an important step toward establishing S5K as the reference tool for BWR stability analysis for KKL, in alignment with Axpo's objectives of enhancing its reactor transient analysis capabilities.

Keywords: SIMULATE5-K, BWR Stability, Sensitivity Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Over recent years, Axpo Power AG (Axpo), Switzerland's largest nuclear utility, has developed a model to simulate transients for the Leibstadt nuclear power plant (KKL), using the best-estimate reactor dynamic code SIMULATE-3K (S3K) [1]. The S3K model is used internally for transient calculations, contributing to scoping studies for KKL and providing independent verification of the analyses conducted by the Reload Licensing Submittal organization. Among all transient events, modeling BWR stability remains particularly challenging due to the complex coupling of neutronics and thermal-hydraulic feedback mechanisms.

The S3K model has been recently validated against KKL stability measurements, representing a significant milestone for its application [2]. In parallel, Studsvik Scandpower (SSP) has developed SIMULATE5-K (S5K) [3], the next-generation best-estimate transient code, which extends the steady-state SIMULATE5 (S5) framework to transient conditions. The new code is designed to address the increasing complexity of modern BWR fuel designs, enhance modeling capabilities, and ensure full consistency between steady-state and transient solutions.

Axpo plans to transition from S3K to S5K, adopting the latter as the future reference tool for transient analyses for KKL. While S5K continues to evolve under active development by SSP, Axpo has launched a comprehensive verification and validation (V&V) program to assess its accuracy and reliability in simulating transients and accident scenarios [4]. In this context, the present study focuses on qualifying

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the S5K core-only model for KKL stability analysis through a systematic sensitivity assessment and comparison with the established S3K model. The objectives are twofold:

1. Verify S5K's physical models relevant to stability phenomena.
2. Optimize the spatio-temporal discretization scheme for BWR stability simulations.

At this stage, the assessment is restricted to the core-only model, since the available S5K version (v2.07.02) has not yet been optimized to support full reactor model calculations that include the peripheral systems. Future work will extend the qualification to the complete reactor model, enabling direct validation against KKL stability measurements and strengthening the confidence in S5K's predictive capabilities.

2. METHODOLOGY

Axpo's KKL core models have been developed and validated for steady-state operation across all KKL operation cycles using the CMS5 package, which integrates the SSP CASMO5 and SIMULATE5 codes. CASMO5 generates few-group cross-section data for fuel assemblies, while SIMULATE5, a 3D multigroup nodal code, performs steady-state reactor core neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations. These validated core models form the basis for subsequent reactor transient simulations performed with the dynamic codes S3K and S5K.

2.1. Axpo Stability Methodology

At Axpo, the stability analysis methodology adopted with S3K is structured into four main steps [1]:

1. For each stability test, the S3K core model is acquired from S5 using the validated CMS5 models
2. For each stability point, an S3K input is prepared incorporating the core model, from S5 restart file, and the peripheral system components
3. The S3K calculation is performed, including steady-state initialization and transient calculation
4. The stability parameters obtained from the transient calculation, i.e. Decay Ratio (DR) and Resonance Frequency (RF), are evaluated

This methodology, applied to both S3K and S5K, constitutes the foundation for the present study, which focuses on evaluating the stability parameters following perturbations applied to the input models.

2.2. S5K Advancements

As the upgraded version of S3K, S5K introduces several advancements and enhanced modeling capabilities compared to its predecessor. The most relevant improvements for BWR applications are summarized below:

- consistency with S5 methods, ensuring coherent steady-state and transient initialization
- Support multi-group neutron diffusion, extending beyond the two-group limitations of S3K
- Improved axial and radial discretization, introducing sub-mesh models consistent with S5
- Fuel-specific two-phase friction correlations, replacing the single-correlation approach used in S3K

2.3. KKL Stability Tests Models

This study examines stability tests performed at KKL for Cycles 10, 13, 19, and 38, with the latter divided into campaigns 1 and 2. These tests, conducted in 1993 (C10), 1996 (C13), 2002 (C19), and 2021 (C38) [2], were requested by the Swiss regulator following modifications in the core or plant system configuration, in order to assess potential changes in the reactor's stability characteristics.

The final dataset consists of 40 stability test cases, providing a comprehensive basis for code benchmarking. The transient code S3K was initially used to develop models for these tests, following

the stability methodology described in Section 2.1. To ensure consistency, the same input models were subsequently adapted for S5K, with syntax updates consistent with the requirements of the new code.

The primary difference between the two codes is their time discretization default settings for BWR stability analysis. S3K uses a 50 ms neutronics time step with 4 thermal-hydraulic (TH) sub-steps, while S5K uses a 100 ms neutronics time step with 5 TH sub-steps. One objective of this study is to recommend an optimal time discretization for S5K stability simulations. Concerning spatial discretization instead, both codes divide the core using one radial node per fuel assembly and 25 axial segments.

The unperturbed S3K and S5K inputs are referred to as reference models, while those modified for the sensitivity analysis are defined as perturbed models.

It should be noted that, since the analysis is limited to the core-only model, a direct validation of the results against experimental measurements cannot be performed at this stage. Therefore, a systematic validation study, including the peripheral systems, will be conducted as part of future work.

2.4. Study Overview

The current section outlines the structure of the analysis carried out in this study.

First, a verification of the steady-state initialization is performed by comparing the two codes under steady-state conditions for various parameters. The purpose is to quantify any differences in the initialization before the transient calculation. Subsequently, the stability parameters are evaluated across the stability tests, and the results are compared to assess the codes' differences in their stability predictions.

These two steps form the basis for the subsequent sensitivity analysis, which involves applying perturbations to specific parameters of interest in the transient code input models and evaluating their impact on the stability parameters. The variations in the outputs are quantified in terms of ΔDR and ΔRF relative to the reference (unperturbed) models, expressed as absolute or percentage differences.

The parameters investigated in this study are grouped into two categories based on the study objectives:

1. Physics Verification: Key physical quantities influencing stability:
 - Operating conditions: Thermal power and core flow varied by $\pm 2\%$
 - Friction loss coefficients: Loss coefficients at the lower tie plate, upper tie plate, and spacer grids modified by $\pm 10\%$
 - Fuel model parameters: Fuel thermal conductivity, fuel-to-cladding gap conductance, and fuel heat capacity varied by $\pm 20\%$
2. Optimization of Numerical Parameters: spatio-temporal discretization parameters affecting numerical diffusion:
 - Spatial discretization: Number of axial nodes increased from 25 (reference) to 60, 75, and 90
 - Time discretization: Case 1: the neutronics time step reduced from 100 ms to 80, 60, 40 and 20 ms, while keeping TH time step constant at 20 ms; Case 2, with a fixed neutronics time step of 100 ms, the TH time step is varied by changing the number of TH sub-steps per neutronics step from 1 (TH time step=100 ms) to 7 (TH time step=14.3 ms). The reference settings use 5 sub-steps (TH time step=20 ms)

3. RESULTS

3.1. Systematic Comparison of Reference Models

3.1.1. Steady-state initialization

The first step compares S5K steady-state results against those from S3K, to quantify any differences in the core initialization between the two code models. Several parameters were analyzed, including key thermal-hydraulic quantities, such as void fraction, axial power peaking factors, and pressure drops at specific core locations.

Due to paper-size limitations, only the void fraction results are presented (Figure 1), while the results for the remaining parameters are summarized without graphical representation. The figure illustrates the results for the two codes together with their difference in percentage terms.

Figure 1. Void fraction comparison between S3K and S5K; reference models

For this parameter, the agreement between the two codes is very good, with all discrepancies below 1.5%. For the other parameters (not illustrated), the two codes exhibit good overall agreement, with discrepancies generally within 5%. However, the core pressure drop was found to be systematically higher in S5K, typically by about +10%. This deviation is expected and has been reported in previous studies [2], which identified as the main root cause the modeling differences of the inlet flow in the two codes. Specifically, S5K provides a more detailed representation of the orifice flow distribution, leading to a larger fraction of flow through the orifice inlet and consequently higher predicted pressure drops.

3.1.2. Stability parameters

In this section, the stability parameters DR and RF for the 40 KKL tests are calculated using S3K and S5K, and the results are compared. The objective is to quantify the discrepancies between the two codes. Figure 2 presents the DR values together with absolute and relative differences, using S3K as reference.

Figure 2. DR comparison between S3K and S5K; reference models

As can be observed, the two codes show good agreement for the Cycle 10 and Cycle 13 tests, whereas the Cycle 19 and particularly the Cycle 38 cases exhibit larger discrepancies, with S5K systematically

predicting lower DR values. Such differences between the codes are expected, given the variations in certain models and correlations implemented in each code.

The larger discrepancies observed for the Cycle 38 tests can be partially attributed to differences in the two-phase friction multiplier treatment. Specifically, S5K allows assigning distinct correlations to different fuel assembly designs, whereas S3K applies a single common multiplier to all fuel types, limiting its flexibility. Nevertheless, further investigation would be required to fully understand the underlying causes, for example, by examining the different fuel designs present in the core during the cycles under consideration. These further analyses are however beyond the scope of the present study, whose objective is to compare the sensitivity of S5K to various parameter changes in stability analysis relative to S3K, rather than to explain the origins of the discrepancies in detail.

Regarding the RF (results not illustrated here due to space limitations), the agreement between the two codes is very good, with all discrepancies remaining below 4%.

3.2. Sensitivity Analysis

This section presents the results of the sensitivity study. It first discusses the analysis of core model and operating condition parameters, aimed at evaluating whether S5K exhibits the expected physical behavior, particularly regarding core stability in response to input variations. It then examines the sensitivity to key spatio-temporal discretization parameters, assessing their impact on the predicted stability characteristics.

3.2.1. Core model parameters and operating conditions

In this section, the key operating conditions and core model parameters are perturbed, and the resulting effects on core stability are examined. The parameters investigated include thermal power and core flow, friction loss coefficients and fuel heat conduction parameters. Due to paper-length limitations, the results for only one representative parameter are illustrated, while the outcomes for the remaining parameters are summarized without graphical presentation.

Figure 3 presents the results of varying the fuel thermal conductivity by $\pm 20\%$ and its effect on the DR as predicted by the two codes.

Figure 3. Sensitivity to fuel conductivity; ΔDR (%)

As shown, both codes exhibit a destabilizing trend with increasing fuel conductivity. This behavior is expected, as higher fuel pellet conductivity enhances heat transfer from the fuel to the coolant, promoting void formation and consequently reducing system stability. Quantitatively, S5K shows a similar level of sensitivity to S3K, with DR variations in the range of 5–8%.

For the remaining parameters (not illustrated), S5K reproduces the expected stability response to all parameter variations, showing full consistency with S3K both qualitatively and quantitatively. The only

exception concerns the fuel-to-cladding gap conductance, where S5K exhibits a mixed trend, i.e. a destabilizing effect (the expected behavior) in some tests and a stabilizing effect in others, whereas S3K consistently predicts a destabilizing effect across all cases. The origin of this inconsistency in S5K remains unclear and will be investigated further in future work.

3.2.2. Axial nodalization

The axial discretization of the core is a key parameter in stability calculations. Typically, the node size is adjusted to balance two opposing factors. On one hand, a larger axial step increases numerical diffusion, which dampens the oscillations and leads to an underestimation of the DR [5]. On the other hand, a finer discretization increases computational time. The ΔDR (%) values obtained with the two codes for different axial nodalizations are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Sensitivity to axial nodalization; reference: 25 nodes; ΔDR (%)

As can be observed, a finer axial discretization consistently increases the S5K-predicted DR due to the reduction of numerical diffusion, which becomes practically negligible with the 90-node model. Comparison between the two codes shows that that DR variations are systematically smaller with S5K, indicating greater robustness, relative to S3K, with respect to axial nodalization changes.

This behavior is likely attributed to the axial re-homogenization methodology implemented in S5K, which enables a more detailed representation of core axial heterogeneities. Moreover, the differences in DR obtained with S5K using 60 and 90 nodes are typically around 1%, compared to a total change of approximately 6% relative to the reference case. This suggests that numerical diffusion can be significantly reduced even with 60 nodes.

Overall, the impact of numerical diffusion on the S5K-predicted DR when using 25 nodes is estimated to be below 10%.

3.2.3. Time discretization

The time-step size is another critical parameter in any transient simulation, as it strongly affects accuracy and computational effort. In general, the neutronics time step is larger and explicitly defined in the transient input, while the thermal-hydraulic time discretization is controlled by specifying the number of sub-steps into which each neutronics step is divided. Under default conditions, S5K employs a neutronics time step of 100 ms and five TH sub-steps, corresponding to a TH time step of 20 ms.

By varying each parameter while keeping the other constant, the study previously conducted on S3K [5] is replicated here for S5K using the 40 KKL stability tests. The results are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Sensitivity to neutronics and thermal-hydraulic time steps; ΔDR (-)

As can be seen, when the TH time-step size is reduced while keeping the neutronics time step constant (red circular markers), the DR systematically increases, consistent with [5]. This is due to reduced numerical diffusion and its associated damping effect, which diminishes with finer TH discretization.

On the other hand, when the neutronics time step is reduced while keeping the TH time step fixed (blue triangular markers), the DR values show a slight decrease. This occurs because a smaller neutronics time step increases the frequency of thermal-hydraulic feedback on the cross sections, thereby enhancing the damping effect, a trend fully consistent with the observations reported in [5].

To further support the optimization of S5K's reference model, the impact of time-step selection on DR is also examined in relation to its effect on computation time. Figure 6 presents an example of this analysis, performed by varying the number of TH sub-steps while keeping the neutronics time step fixed at 100 ms.

Figure 6. Sensitivity to the number of TH sub-steps for a fixed neutronics time step (100 ms); reference TH number: 5; errorbars corresponding to 1- σ ; ΔDR (%) vs ΔCPU time (%)

The x-axis shows the ΔCPU time (%), relative to the reference setting of five sub-steps (TH time step = 20 ms), whereas the y-axis shows the ΔDR (%), determined with respect to the same reference. Each data point represents the average value and standard deviation of all stability tests.

From the results, an optimal range is identified when the number of TH sub-steps is set between 4 and 7. For example, using 7 sub-steps yields a ~5% increase in DR at the cost of approximately 10% longer computation time (about 9 additional minutes per calculation). The optimal configuration therefore depends on achieving a balance between computational efficiency and the reduction of numerical diffusion within this range.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study represents an important step in the qualification of S5K for BWR stability analysis and the optimization of its input models, thereby supporting Axpo's transition from S3K for transient analyses for KKL. A systematic sensitivity analysis was conducted using core-only models of 40 KKL historic stability tests.

S5K successfully reproduces expected physical trends in system stability, confirming physics verification for most parameters. The only exception is the fuel-to-cladding gap conductance, which showed an inconsistent behavior. Further investigation is needed to determine whether this deviation reflects a true physical phenomenon or a modeling artifact.

Analyses on the numerical parameters support the optimization of the spatio-temporal discretization for stability analysis and demonstrate the trade-off between reducing numerical diffusion and increasing computational cost when refining the axial nodalization or time discretization.

In conclusion, the findings provide a robust foundation for adopting S5K as the reference tool for transient analysis at KKL, strengthening Axpo's capabilities for reactor dynamics calculations. The results confirm that the core-only model reasonably reproduces core behavior, providing a useful basis for future extensions to incorporate the peripherals. As a future step, comprehensive verification and validation against plant measurements will be carried out once the full S5K model is completed.

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